

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES (PROBLEMATIC TEACHING TECHNOLOGY) IN THE TEACHING OF ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the use of pedagogical technology in teaching English. In this, students can work on themselves, acquire new knowledge independently, find various options for getting out of a given problem situation and come to the right solution while analyzing them, develop mental activity, be able to apply the knowledge they have acquired in the future, make decisions. skills are discussed.

The use of pedagogical technologies in the teaching of foreign languages is the demand of the time today, through which the learner can master the subject quickly and effectively, through which the student develops the ability to work independently and creates a positive thinking environment. One such method is problem-based learning technology. The main task of this technology is to help students to effectively acquire knowledge of the English language, and to create skills to solve existing problems by creatively approaching new situations that will arise in their future professional activities. The main essence of this technology is to invite students to creative thinking and discussion through educational methods where the teacher of science proposes ways to solve the questions and approves or rejects them by asking questions.

In addition to applying previously learned material, or recalling new words and phrases, while looking for answers to a problem, one must also refer to new synonyms, homonyms, or antonyms and phrases in order to learn how to utilize them [1-5]. When utilizing this technology, it's crucial for students to identify the right issue and work as a team to resolve it [1]. For this reason, the produced issue scenario should be developed in a way that it is composed of the educational contents conveyed on the subject, and students should work and master it autonomously. When studying a problematic issue in English language instruction, the student should be able to independently enter the situation, comprehend it, and assess it. The steps of creating a problem scenario in English include preparation, familiarization, analysis, and ultimate decision-making [2].

The first step in creating a problem situation is for the English teacher to set a problem that is a logical continuation of the English language course, the complexity of the task should be based on the abilities of the students, and there should be a directive for the students to complete the tasks. The scientific instructor provides a general description of the task's nature and content in the introduction. He also welcomes discussion from the kids at the same

time. The presented problem is evaluated and debatably debated in a group setting during the analysis and final decision-making phases.

One significant benefit of this technology is that it helps students develop the analytical and problem-solving abilities they will need in their future careers. As a result, employing this technology to organize English classes encourages pupils to think independently and creatively.

The following are examples of writing skills for English language teaching technological problems.

- The teacher sets up a challenging writing assignment, such the theme "Describing persons". Training sessions on this subject are planned; students are given a list of adjectives and instructed to determine which ones describe positive or negative qualities. They are then instructed to select five of the adjectives and write five justification sentences for each one, followed by a brief paragraph. In order to tackle difficulties creatively, we break the class into smaller groups. Conditions are set up for conversation by breaking people up into smaller groups.

- to solve the problem, students use the knowledge they have acquired in the previous topics, students in a small group come to a generalized solution using the given adjectives. In this way, not only the ability of creative thinking develops in every student, but also the level of learning increases. The activity of using academic words in solving the problem of "describing a person's appearance" is increasing.

Students learn the four abilities of learning the English language as well as working with a group, supporting the perspectives of group members, and expressing their thoughts freely in a team by posing a challenging issue in English language instruction. Forming skills and the capacity for autonomous thought. When selecting a challenging setting, it is appropriate to plan based on current social network occurrences, taking into account all English teaching abilities. The students will be more engaged and have more opportunity to find a solution if the events and debates are more well-known. Adding strategies to English language instruction that encourage autonomous study and a creative approach to each topic while posing problems for pupils to solve. Positive outcomes are obtained when teaching English utilizing technology that is problem-based [2]. When a difficult circumstance is presented during instruction, the student uses the previously learned information to resolve the issue. The student demonstrates with examples whether he agrees with the issue, disagrees with it, or is neutral while writing essays for and against the specified position (agree or disagree essay). In turn, this appears to be a natural progression given the purpose and core elements of this technology.

When teaching English with problem-based education technology, many formats can be employed [1,3,5]:

1. The scientific instructor fully discusses the challenging question and offers a solution. In this instance, the instructor promotes individual thought among the class by posing queries. For instance, tasks on the subject of creating a CV or resume are provided, and students are observed as they employ the clauses and words that make up the CV or resume writing process.

2. The scientific instructor poses a problem question and solely describes the task's topic. Students must work individually. For example, if the challenge of writing Letters of requesting and offering advise is presented, characteristics of these letters that differ from others are addressed, and independent study on the topic is necessary.
3. The science teacher creates a problematic situation. In this, students are directed to think independently to find an answer to a problematic question.
4. The science teacher does not give the meaning and solution of the problem situation but "approaches" it. In this case, students get out of the problem situation with a creative approach.

When employing this technology, an English instructor should not provide pupils solutions. Only then will the instructor assist the pupils in developing the abilities of seeking new information and understanding. As a consequence, the student will be able to solve mental issues independently, make conclusions, generalize, and apply them in future problem scenarios based on the sequence of evidence offered by the knowledge he has received.

To summarize, students are able to work on themselves, gain new knowledge independently, identify multiple possibilities for getting out of a difficult scenario, and accurately analyze them as a consequence of the use of problem-based teaching technology in English instruction. It aids in the development of mental activity in solving problems, the ability to apply newly learned knowledge in the future, and the expansion of knowledge through decision-making abilities.

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